

IMPORTANCE OF ENGLISH LITERATURE IN LEARNING

ENGLISH

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Abstract: This study intends to focus on English literature in developing four language skills like vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation of all English language learners. This study also pays attention benefits and drawbacks of learning English with literature. Role of different genres of literature plays vital role in this field. This style of learning also helps to explore human psychology and critical thinking. Students will learn language from other perspective, from “best” products of English. Data were collected from university students and teachers through qualitative approach.

Key words: language skills, classroom language, literary competence, grammar, genres, foreign language teaching.

INTRODUCTION

If you're thinking about learning English, it is always good to know a little about the origins and history of the language you are learning. The English language originates from the Old Germanic, Norwegian and Anglo-Norman languages. Modern English was used in the 14th century, and the closest languages to English are Dutch and West Flemish. 339 million people speak English as a first language and 603 million as a second language. It is an official language in 67 countries and 27 non-independent countries such as Hong Kong. Dr. Johnson's Dictionary of 1755 lays down the rules of English grammar and spelling. This dictionary was the first to fully document the English lexicon and is one of the most popular dictionaries in history, taking over 8 years to create. William Shakespeare was an imminent English

poet, actor and playwright. Above all, he introduced thousands of words and phrases into the English language literature shows different types of characters in its own style. Literature has been proven as a great tool to approach English language and English culture. Literature gives many new words, learning these words helps in the improvement of vocabulary in language. Literature is a complex art.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Literary works such as poetries, novels, stories, or plays should be used in foreign language teaching because these works include all the features needed to teach a foreign language. Collie and Slater give four reasons why a language teacher should use literary texts in the classroom; serve as original materials, enrich the language because it provides different features of written language, increase understanding of different cultures, and allow personal participation because imagination guides students from the structure to the story itself. According to Tasnin's quoted information, the advantages of literature as a language teaching tool can be summarized as follows:

1. Literature is a very interesting way of learning a language.
2. Examples of different ways of writing are given in the literature, as well as information on different uses of the original language.
3. Literature is a good means of increasing vocabulary.
4. Encourages students to develop various reading skills.
- 5 It can be used as a springboard for interesting discussions or writing.
6. It includes both emotions and intellect, which promotes motivation and can contribute to the personal development of the reader.
7. English literature (general) is part of the target culture and therefore has value as part of the general education of students.
8. Encourages critical and creative thinking.
9. Enriches students' knowledge about the world.
- 10 It makes students aware of various human situations and conflicts.

Povey mentions that "Literature will increase all language skills because literature will extend linguistic knowledge". Thus, literature can serve as effective and valuable material to improve students' writing, reading listening and speaking skills. A story with a number of four or five characters is given to students to be read as homework. The next lesson, having warmed up by summarizing the plot and paying attention to some chosen sentences to enable students enjoy the beauty of literature, students are divided into groups in class according to the number of the characters in the story. The teacher assigns a character to each group and each group as an individual writes a letter to another group telling their circumstances and they may ask for help, offer help, make a deal etc. So, each group representing a character from the story writes and receives a letter and each group has to answer the received letter. A group member reads their group's letter in front of the class and a student from the addressed group reads their answer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As a result of this study students will learn creativity and inspiration, develop essential skills. This gives a chance to sharpen ability to write, read, analyze and persuade. Also it encourages students to pick up more books, learn whole range of vocabulary. English literature teaches students about culture, history, analysis of themes within texts.

English language and literature education shall enhance the language skills of students. First, guide students to do a large number of reading exercises to improve students' language skills. When teaching English language and literature, every teacher emphasizes the importance of feeling the language, but learning the language requires a lot of reading exercises, which means that students need to read and collect. Therefore, in order to develop good language skills, teachers should guide students to read a lot, from quantitative to qualitative changes, improve students' language skills. Second, explain the educational goals of English literature, guide students to conscious reading, improve language skills.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, most of the indicators indicate a strong preference for teaching literature in English classes to improve the skills and knowledge of students. As it is generally accepted, it is considered very useful to include literature in language teaching. Using literature as a resource in the English classroom enhances creativity and ability to write, read and appreciate the language. It also encourages speaking skills and personal expression. This exercise leads to the improvement of students' skills in developing critical and analytical conclusions of literary texts. Literature is the best way for people to understand that language is best learned by reading literature. All the above advantages cannot be gained by studying grammar or academic books that students can see in high school. Literature is the key to the right path to the benefits of a new language, because reading literature allows students to independently choose for the diversity of their culture and knowledge

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